

A 1.6mW 320x240 pixel vision sensor for event detection

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Abstract—This paper reports on a low-power vision sensor embedding a custom algorithm for event detection. Anomalous or suspicious motions occurring in the scene are isolated from the background by continuously monitoring the time variation of the pixel intensity with respect to two thresholds that are dynamically updated. Pixels whose intensity is out of the range defined by these thresholds are considered as a part of a possibly anomalous activity and they are called hot pixels. The sensor has been fabricated in a 110nm CMOS technology. It delivers gray-scale images in QVGA format and related hot-pixel bitmaps at 15 fps with a power consumption of 1.6mW.

Keywords—Video surveillance; event detection; dynamic background subtraction; smart sensors; low-power vision

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last years, a big effort has been devoted to the development of ultra-low power electronic components thanks also to the huge market of mobile devices and the increasing interest in IoT technology [1]. In this respect, vision represents one of the most challenging technologies for battery-operated long-lasting operation, where real-time massive parallel processing and low-power performance need to coexist [2][3][4].

In this paper, we report an architecture of an always-active vision sensor embedding energy-efficient algorithm for event detection through programmable background subtraction and motion detection [5][6]. Images are acquired at frame-rate and filtered out, row-by-row, by a custom array of processors aimed at subtracting the background of each pixel from its signal and detecting any suspicious activities. Updated

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the vision sensor architecture.

parameters of the algorithm are stored into internal SRAM to be retrieved during next frame for successive event processing. The presented vision chip is interfaced with a processor as part of a wireless sensor node for surveillance applications. In a typical application, the chip continuously acquires images, extracts hot-pixels and delivers them to the processor in order to detect any suspicious event to occur. Since the number of hot-pixels in a scene is only limited to a few percent of the imager resolution, minimum computing power is required for the processor to extract alert information.

II. SENSOR ARCHITECTURE

The basic architecture of the sensor is shown in Fig.1. The 320x240 APS imager is read out by 320 column-wise Amplifiers as part of the 320 Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADC). 160 out of 320 ADCs are part of the 160 digital Processors to implement the pixel-level algorithm and to detect hot-pixels. Since the algorithm is applied only on a quarter of the pixel array (120x160 pixels - Quarter QVGA), a 240x160x10-bit SRAM to store the temporary values of the algorithm. Gray-scale imager and related hot-pixel bitmap are delivered off-chip row-by-row.

Hot Pixel Detection

Let V_i be the i th frame after down-sampling. For each pixel x of V_i , the intensity level $V_i(x)$ is compared with two thresholds $V_i^m(x)$ and $V_i^M(x)$, that depend on x and are updated dynamically frame by frame. If $V_i(x)$ is outside of the interval $\Gamma = [V_i^m(x) - \Delta_{HOT}, V_i^M(x) + \Delta_{HOT}]$, then x is labeled as a hot pixel, i.e. it may correspond to an event of interest. Otherwise,

Fig. 2. Basic operating principle of the chip embedded algorithm referred to a single pixel. Vpix line represents the pixel signal behavior over 200 frames; Vmax and Vmin are the two thresholds following the pixel with different time constant which depend on the specific case.

the pixel is said to be cold. Hot pixels are stored in a bitmap, i.e. a binary image where white (black, resp.) pixels are hot (cold, resp.).

The parameter $\Delta_{HOT} > 0$ is an integer number, input by the user. The thresholds $V_i^m(x)$ and $V_i^M(x)$ are positive real-valued numbers with $V_i^m(x) > V_i^M(x)$ for any pixel x . At the first frame V_0 the sensor does not perform event detection, but uses V_0 to initialize $V_i^m(x)$ and $V_i^M(x)$, precisely: $V_1^m(x) = V_0(x) - \Delta_{HOT}$ and $V_1^M(x) = V_0(x) + \Delta_{HOT}$.

For each $i \geq 1$, $V_i^m(x)$ and $V_i^M(x)$ are updated by these rules:

- 1) if $V_i^m(x) \leq V_i(x)$ then $V_{i+1}^m(x) = V_i^m(x) + \Delta_{OPEN}$;
- 2) if $V_i^m(x) > V_i(x)$ then $V_{i+1}^m(x) = V_i^m(x) - \Delta_{CLOSE}$;
- 3) if $V_i^M(x) \geq V_i(x)$ then $V_{i+1}^M(x) = V_i^M(x) - \Delta_{OPEN}$;
- 4) if $V_i^M(x) < V_i(x)$ then $V_{i+1}^M(x) = V_i^M(x) + \Delta_{CLOSE}$;

where Δ_{OPEN} and Δ_{CLOSE} range over $(0, +\infty)$ and $\Delta_{OPEN} > \Delta_{CLOSE}$ are input decided by the user. By these rules, the thresholds $V_i^m(x)$ and $V_i^M(x)$ tend to “chase” the signal $V_i(x)$, and thus dynamically update the information about the activity status of the pixel. An example of threshold updating is shown in Fig. 2.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The vision sensor has been fully tested at 15 fps. Powered with 3.3V for the analog part and 1.2V for the digital one, the total measured power consumption is 1.6 mW when the sensor delivers both gray-level images and hot-pixel bitmap.

A system prototype has been developed where the sensor is interfaced with a PC through USB in order the user to set the sensor and algorithm parameters and to save videos (gray-scale and binary) for successive analysis. The prototype shown in Fig. 3 has been used for acquisition in different use case scenarios reproducing some alert conditions: a boat approaching the beach (Fig. 4), escaping people, car moving out of the road.

The performance on the hot pixel detection has been measured on a set of 30 videos acquired by the sensor in

Fig. 3. Vision sensor prototype. The chip is controlled through an FPGA which provides the interface with a PC.

Fig. 4. Example of the sensor operation. Left: QVGA grayscale image; right: quarter QVGA hot-pixel bitmap after erosion.

different, isolated places, where some volunteers simulated anomalous activities, usually in daylight or evening, like walking or driving in forbidden areas, carrying objects and/or people by cars or boats, climbing gates. On average, the mean number of frames per video is 718, while the mean number of frames corresponding to an event of interest is 423. The mean luminance of the frames is 87 LSB.

The sensor detected on average the 90.27% of the frames corresponding to an event, while it missed the 9.73%. In the case of missed frame, we observed that the object to be detected was very far from the sensor, so that its size in the image was very small: in this case, the group of the hot pixels corresponding to the event was rejected because considered as noise. The percentage of false positives (frames not corresponding to an event, but where the sensor found hot pixels) is about the 24.15 %: False positives are usually due to the movement of not interesting objects, like for instance the foliage. We observe that these movements are usually ‘adsorbed’ by the threshold updating mechanism, that tends to inhibit the hot pixel detection in regions characterized by repetitive movements.

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